

Performance of cold-tolerant varieties in western hills of Nepal

B. R. Sthapit, Crop Science Section, Lumle Agricultural Centre, P.O. Box No. 1, Pokhara, Kaski, Nepal

A large portion of rice in Nepal is grown at 1000-2000 m above sea level, where low temperatures cause cold damage. Most varieties grown in high altitudes are indigenous. We evaluated 28 genotypes in 1989 at our Chhomro off-station research site (2000 m above sea level). They were indigenous varieties Raksali, Palung 2, and Chhomro local and materials obtained from IRRI, and the Nepal Rice Improvement Program, Parwanipur, and Botany Division, Khumaltar.

Water temperature during anthesis (Oct-Nov) was 20.2 °C; mean minimum temperatures were 15.1-16.5 °C; mean maximum, 16.3-19.7 °C. During early seedling growth (Jun-Jul), minimum temperatures were 14.5-16.4 °C and maximum temperatures, 21.9-23.1 °C.

Agronomic traits for cold tolerance were good in some exotic varieties (see table). Spikelet sterility was 100% in all genotypes except Chhomro local (14%) and Seto Bhakunde (25%). Those local varieties produced some yield.

Internationally known cold-tolerant

Some agronomic traits^a of selected cold-tolerant rice genotypes at Chhomro (altitude 2000 m), Nepal, 1989.

Genotype	Plant vigor (1-9 scale)	Tillering ability (1-9 scale)	Cold tolerance (1-9 scale)	Panicle exertion (1-9 scale)	Sheath rot (1-9 scale)
Akiyudaka	7	9	5	5	3
Chhomro Local (check)	3	5	5	1	1
Fuji-102	9	9	7	5	3
IRI-353	3	5	3	5	3
K335	9	9	7	5	3
NR10157-2B-17-2	9	9	9	5	7
Palung 2	7	7	9	5	5
Rakshali	5	5	5	5	3
Rodina	9	9	7	5	5
Stejaree 45	9	9	5	3	3
Bhutan 11	9	9	5	3	3
B4190E-CW-139-29-176	7	5	9	5	3
B4448E-35R-1	7	7	9	5	3
Cheonmabyeo	9	7	7	3	3
Chhomro (check)	5	3	5	1	1
IR15579-166	7	7	9	5	3
IR23325-R-R-B-7-2-2	5	5	9	3	3
IR26036-2-2-2-3	7	7	7	5	7
MI01	7	5	5	3	3
NR10157-2B-13-1	7	7	7	5	3
NR10157-2B-13-5	5	5	1	5	5
NR10157-2B-17-1	9	5	7	5	7
NR10167-2B-7	3	5	7	5	3
NR10164-2B-14	7	3	9	5	7
NR10167-2B-16	7	7	9	5	7
NR10177-B-11	7	5	9	5	3
NR10180-B-13-3	7	5	7	5	7
NR10180-B-13-4	7	7	7	5	5
Seto Bhakunde	3	5	5	1	3

^aBy Standard evaluation system for rice scale. Only Chhomro Local, Chhomro, and Seto Bhakunde gave some yield.

materials such as China 1039, Akiyudaka, and Stejaree 45 failed to set grain.

This suggests a need to evaluate more

indigenous varieties from the Himalayan belt for use in the breeding program for cold-tolerant rices. ■

Screening rice for temperature tolerance in northern Nigeria

W. N. Umeh, National Cereals Research Institute, P.M.B. 1022, Birnin Kebbi, Sokoto State, Nigeria

Most rice production in Nigeria is restricted to the wet season, with a long fallow between seasons. Irrigation schemes in the northern states provide an opportunity to overcome contingent drought and increase rice production through better land utilization.

Development of temperature-tolerant rice varieties would help reduce the long fallow in areas with 3-4 mo of cold weather (Nov-Jan/Feb) and 3-4 mo hot weather (Feb-May).

The cold season is characterized by no rainfall, high and frequent cold harmattan wind. low minimum but relatively high maximum temperature, low relative humidity, hazy and dusty atmosphere, and high evapotranspiration (Table 1).

(Harmattan is the northeasterly cold wind that blows from Europe, across the Mediterranean and Sahara desert, and down the coast of West Africa.)

Atmospheric demand for moisture (indicated by piche evaporation) is high from

Table 1. Climatological data for cold and hot months.^a Northern Nigeria, 1988.

Month	Rainfall (mm)	Temperature (°C)		Wind speed (kg/h)	Piche evaporation (ml/d)
		Maximum	Minimum		
October	0	36	23	158.40	14.5
November	0	35	20	188.22	19.5
December	0	30.4	17.3	245.47	21.9
January	0	30.9	17.6	294.92	23.9
February	0	34.3	19.7	283.20	26.6
March	0	38.8	26.0	261.55	29.7
April	5.8	40.0	28.2	243.1	21.6
May	Trace	40.3	29.3	250.2	19.8

^aCourtesy of the Meteorological Department, Sokoto Station, Nigeria.